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Effect Of Migration On National Security In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the effect of migration on national security in Nigeria. The study adopted three objectives which investigated the causes and effect of migration, and proffer effective strategies for managing migration in national security. The theory of transnationalism is adopted as its theoretical construct. The study adopted the field survey research that is qualitative and quantitative in nature. Findings revealed that porous borders, abuse of ECOWAS protocol, globalization/manpower problem, inadequate cooperation between security agencies, educational opportunities, lack of social safety, poor governance, corruption, lack of social justice, equity, and fair play, youth unemployment were causes of migration while infiltration of terrorists, banditry, instability, diseases, and economic down turn are identified effect of migration in national security. The study recommended amongst others that government should adopt policies that will transform border areas from deplorable conditions and put in place effective and efficient machinery that would speed up developmental process. Also, there should be inter-border cooperation with neighbouring government to checkmate the movement of criminals and contraband goods.

Keywords: Migration, National Security, Unemployment, Cooperation and Trans-Border Crime.

INTRODUCTION

The continued influx of Nigeriens to Northern Nigeria engenders conflicts over the scarce food resources in the area. The food crisis in Nigeria has also impacted negatively on the pastoralists and the herdsmen who move down south in search of pasture for their animals. In pastoral areas, production is 66% below national needs (). Since the beginning of creation, humans have always involved themselves in movement activities. This has been a major feature in the history of Africa and the entire globe generally (Akanji, 2012). This indicates that historical background of migration can be traced as far back as the existence of man, most especially when man desired to go in search of food during various famine seasons. Okeoghene (2017) opines that virtually all individuals and nation states have one or two traces of migration history (Internal and international) mostly influenced by two factors these are the “pull” and “push” factors. It is said to be internal or international. Internal migration explains the movement of individuals within same geographical territory which in this case can be from rural to urban or from Lagos to Abuja. International migration has to do with the crossing of borders or international boundaries such as Cameroon to Nigeria described as South-South Migration, Nigeria to United States of America described also as South-North Migration. For International migration (emigration and immigration) to take place, the sending state, the receiving state and the migrant is involved in the migration process. Aliome (2019) opines that migration and national security are generally regarded as complex phenomena with many perspectives. In fact, the multidimensionality of the concepts requires special approach and

development of measures to secure them. However, due to the rising case of globalization and increase and desires of migrants to be part of a nation state at all cost or become a resident in their favourite destinations the international system is consciously concerned about this high rate of movements of migrants across borders (Immigration act, 2015). This globalization which has unfolded itself in different phases has raised alarm of great benefits and opportunities around the globe. This benefit ranges from job opportunities, international education certifications, interconnectedness, international relations between countries creating avenue for interdependence most especially in the aspect of manpower (Fayomi, 2013). International migration (emigration and immigration) as a major and popular economic factor can revive a nation state, it has the capacity to develop a nation state through other means such as filling the nation state's labour force with quality skills and expertise for maximum productivity as earned results. Due to this perceived opportunities International Migration became a popular culture and trend in our present world. Unfortunately, the Nigerian state shares borders with Cameroon located at the eastern part of Nigeria, Chad to the Northern part of Nigeria while the South-West Nigeria region is bordered by Benin Republic. The porous borders which are mostly economical to her fellow West African neighbours keeps Nigeria at disadvantage, as they are majorly unprotected thereby threatening the national security of the Nigeria (Abiodun, 2015). Nwagwugwu (2015) avers that though the movement is perceived to bring peace and unity to West Africans as well as to promote trade which would lead to economic growth of the West African states but recent studies prove that the poor borders of Nigeria is largely responsible for the infiltration of the foreign Fulani Herders, Boko Haram insurgents, ISWAP West Africa, bandits and other forms of terrorism which have claimed more lives and destruction of property in many Nigerian states. Cross-border recruitment of young people as mercenaries in armed conflict is all too common in the arc of territory extending from Guinea-Bissau to Côte d'Ivoire, combined with many other cross-border problems in West Africa, including small arms, mercenaries, illegal check-points and drug-trafficking. This, as a matter of fact, causes insecurities in the domestic internal affairs of each nation as well as in the region (Philemon, Manasseh and Godiya, 2019).

Undoubtedly, this has caused more national security threats in the country. More so, due to the lack of national security among other reasons in the Nigerian state the issue of emigration has been a trend in Nigeria for graduates, experts and hustlers. The hustlers most especially who are in search for a greener pasture most times walk through the porous borders out of the nation state (Akinyemi, 2013). Nosiri and Ohazurike (2016) further stress that the extent to which states protect their territory against any internal crime and potential aggressors or threat depends on the level of their ability or capability to achieve adequate national security. The classification of whether a state is a weak, strong and failed state depends on the level of its capability to protect its citizens and international borders (Okumu, 2011).

Okeoghene (2017) observes that the poor border security has gone a long way to aid the operation of the terrorist group like Boko Haram. The problem of securing Nigeria border helps the Boko Haram to adequately launch several successful attacks in Nigeria and other neighbouring countries killing thousands of people and displaced millions of people (Menner, 2014). The porous nature of the border has enabled the terrorists to purchase or traffic weapons and travel to other neighbouring countries for other assistance. This has led to several training camps in Chad, Niger Republic and Cameroon. Okumu (2011) asserts that insecure borders have greatly contributed to severe security threats such as insurrection, incursion and terrorist activity.

Following these developments, the Nigerian government took several initiatives to reposition the economy for improved performance and enhance national security. Despite some measures adopted by the government which include change in military fighting tactics, purchase of fighter jets, policing bodies such as Vigilante Groups, Nigeria Immigration Service, amongst others to expel or curb the menace associated with international migration, the problems remain unabated.

Theoretical Framework

Theory of Transnationalism: The theory of transnationalism was popularized in the early 20th century by Randolph Bourne which grown out of the increased interconnectivity between people and receding

economic and social significance of boundaries among nation-state (Transnationalism, 2016). Transnationalism talks about the process where immigrants forge and sustain multi-stranded social relations that link together their societies of origin and that of their host country (Rosemberg, Boutain & Mohammed, 2016). It is based on increased functional integration and multiple interaction or links of people, states and institutions across borders or beyond state boundaries, which can affect the capability of states. This increased interaction is facilitated by globalization. This theory viewed that the increase in interaction between non-state actors (as a result of globalization) across borders has led to several impact on the capability of states. Therefore, the constant cross border activities or interactions affect the domestic policies of state actors (which can reduce the importance of states). This transnational interaction can take place in one country while the effects are seen in another country (Soehi & Waldinger, 2012). This theory or approach “emphasizes the ways in which nations are no longer able to contain or control the disputes or negotiation through which social groups annex a global dimension to their meaningful practices, the notion of diaspora brings to the fore the racial dynamics underlying the international division of labour and the economic turmoil of global capital” (Transnationalism, 2016). The theory of transnationalism has the following assumptions:

- i. Persons are not bound to place, as much, as they are to space and technologies of place.
- ii. There is cultural connectivity and reproduction and human mobility. Meaning that individuals or immigrants maintained cultural ties with their parent country and reproduce these cultural-related activities in their host country when the need arises.
- iii. Some immigrants stay abreast of and influence the political-related occurrences of both their home and host country.
- iv. The increased cross-border activities and interactions affect the capability of states. (Rosemberg et al, 2016).

This theory is relevant or can be applied to this study because there has existed several increased relations or interaction between people or non-state actors beyond Nigerian borders. With the help of globalization, Nigerian citizens have maintained ties with citizens in other countries with ease. These interactions can be in form of economic, social, cultural and political interaction. The constant ties or interactions of people from different countries within and across Nigerian borders most times serves as a problem to state’s capability on how to ensure effective border security and national security in Nigeria. As people interact across borders by engaging in illegal or illicit trade activities and other organized crimes, they most times devise several means on how to sustain such relations across borders. This can lead to several challenges to state’s capability to control and manage its borders from unnecessary infiltrations that can pose a threat to sovereignty and survival of the state.

Concept of Migration

According to Iheanacho and Ughaerumba (2015), migration can be traced to the existence of the first set of humans on earth. Migration has taken various patterns such as slave trade, colonization, urbanization, industrialization and globalization. Movement of persons (migrants) from one place to another has been a trend adopted by various individuals. International Migration in Nigeria can be traced from the pre-colonial era (precisely slave trade era) to colonial and post-colonial era. Although the nation-state was not recognized as Nigeria as at then as it had a kingdom and empire structure. This made it difficult to be described as internal or international structure. The most important is to note that migration in Africa (Nigeria) can be traced to this era. During these eras migration was both forced and voluntary. In Nigeria, during the 1960s International Migration became the new trend and was at its increase as Nigerians and other Africans left their respective states for Europe while the South-South pathways of migration also existed, as Africans migrated to various parts of West African neighbouring states mostly for trade purposes (regional integration).

Muhammad (2021) defines migration as the movement of a person or group of persons from one geographical unit to another across an administrative or political border, who wish to settle definitely or temporarily in a place other than their place of origin. Migration is also seen as the movement of people from one place in the world to another for the purpose of taking up permanent or semi-permanent residence, usually across a political boundary. Migration is the movement of people from one place to another either permanently (in which case they settle down) or temporary (which case they return home after a period of stay). It has been a feature of geography from time immemorial. In ancient times, people move from one place to another in search of better agricultural land, richer hunting grounds, better fisheries, abundant commercial activities, refugees from hostile armies etc (Dahiru, 2017).

Okeoghene (2017) notes that from the early days, Africans have through the ages moved from one place to another as cattle herders, traders, invaders or refugees. There was also been a considerable migration in West Africa sub-region resulting from economic, social and political problems. This phenomenon has been in existing even before the independence of African countries and even before the idea of international boundaries which received prominence in 1884 that resulted in partition of Africa at Berlin. As a result of this partition by colonial masters, free movement of people and goods across the borders were curtailed and various regulations requiring certain formalities to be accomplished before admittance of non-citizens were introduced. However, in spite of the control measures, irregular immigrants still cross international boundaries mostly through unapproved routes/entry ports.

Concept of National Security

According to Adebakin and Raimi (2012) national security covers critical dimensions, viz: economic security, political security, food security, health security, environmental security, personal security and community security. However, nation like Nigeria has its own peculiar security threat determined by the aforementioned dimensions. Thus, this paper is concern with migrant threats to Nigeria's national security as exemplified by the activities of illegal immigrants.

Adeola and Oluyemi (2012) refers to security as "the situation that exists as a result of the establishment of measures for the protection of persons, information and property against hostile persons, influences and actions". It is the existence of conditions within which people in a society can go about their normal daily activities without any threat to their lives or properties. It embraces all measures designed to protect and safeguard the citizenry and the resources of individuals, groups, business and the nation against sabotage or violent occurrences (Dambazau, 2007). Igbuzor (2011) notes that security demand safety from chronic threats and protection from harmful disruption. Ani (2010) argues that the term 'national security' came into use in the twentieth century, particularly after the World War II. Edem (2010) conceptualized national security as the ability of the Nigerian State to successfully pursue her national interest, being able to protect the values of the state and being able to maintain the same. According to Dambazau (2007) security of the state in the traditional sense meant the protection of the state, its boundaries, people, institutions, and values, from external attack. It is therefore a collection of plans, actions and institutions built by a state in order to protect themselves from both internal and external attack. It is the act of promoting the core values of a state that would enhance the protection of lives and properties of the citizenry (Okene, 2010).

National security refers to the requirement needed to maintain the survival of the state through the use of economic power, diplomacy, power protection and political power. Therefore, security of any kind is related with national security and its potency needs not to be undermined, hence the need for concerted and urgent step in order to entrench and sustain peace and security at our nation border. It should be noted that security at our nation borders is very instrumental to its survival. This is why border post were constructed at the border not only to deter smuggling but to prevent irregular entry into the country. National security is tempered with, when there is an uncontrolled movement of people across the borders; this tends to increase the rate of social vices in the recipient country.

From the forgoing definitions, we can deduce that the concept of security has many connotations as being put forward by divergent scholars and security analyst differently in international domain. This therefore has to do with whatever endangers the survival of the individual as well as the state. In a very popular usage, security refers to lack of threat; its opposite is called insecurity which is what has remained an issue at Nigeria’s border. The main essence of national security is the protection of the national interest/value of a state and upholding what the state believes to be valuable to it and its people. Some issues of national value can be found in the norm of a country i.e. its Constitution, from actions of government or other state policies that are manifest from its relationship and interaction with other states. Security is imperative and has a direct link with the concept of border which needs protective measures to curtail activities geared towards endangering the lives and properties of people and also compromising the integrity of the state. Border security has an implication on the national security this is because the proliferation of small arms and light weapons has brought about ethnic and communal conflicts in many countries; this is also linked to trans-border arms trafficking. There has been growing concerns by Nigerians for lack of effective security at the nation’s borders, this is because the terrorist make use of this means to penetrate and perpetuate illicit activities at the national borders, this calls for more attention at effective management of our borders.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study is field survey research which involves the use of triangulation (primary and secondary data). Nigeria has a total population of 215,175,364 (National Bureau of Statistics, 2022). However, the sample size of 400 respondents was determined using the Taro Yamane’s formula. Data were obtained through the administration of structured questionnaire to the respondents. The instruments were tested and re-tested on 10 purposive selected respondents in an interval of 2 weeks after the initial test using the percentage of response to determine its reliability. The questionnaire was structured into two sections. Section A entails the demographic attributes while the Section B centred on questions used in testing the causes and effect of migration on national security. The 4-likert scale was used in rating the responses with options of strongly agree (4), agree (3), disagree (2), and strongly disagree (1). Data obtained were presented using tables and percentages. Simple percentage statistical method was used to determine degree of acceptability.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Socio-demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

The frequency and percentage distribution of the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents is presented in this section. These include age, marital status, level of education, and occupation amongst others.

Table 1: Frequency and Percentage distribution of Respondents by Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
18-20yrs	24	8.0
21-24yrs	14	4.7
25-29yrs	40	13.3
30-34yrs	52	17.3
35-39yrs	61	20.3
40-44yrs	51	17.0
45-49yrs	58	19.3
Total	300	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

The result presented in Table 1 above shows frequency and percentage distribution of respondents by age. The table revealed that 18-20yrs, 21-24yrs, 25-29yrs, 30-34yrs, 35-39yrs, 40-44yrs and 45-49yrs have frequencies of 24, 14, 40, 52, 61, 51 and 68 respectively. This indicates that majority of the respondents

are within the age bracket of 35-39 and 45-49 years representing 20.3% and 19.3% of the population of this study respectively.

Table 2: Frequency and Percentage distribution of Respondents by Level of Education

Education	Frequency	Percentage
No formal education	3	1.0
Primary Education	7	2.3
Secondary Education	120	40.0
OND/NCE	109	36.3
B Sc.	50	16.7
Higher Degree	10	3.3
Others	1	0.3
Total	300	100.0

Source: Fieldwork, 2020

The result in Table 4 above shows that the highest number (120) of the respondents, representing 40.0%, is those with secondary school education. This figure is followed by those with OND/NCE with 109, representing 36.3% of the respondents. This indicates that most of the respondents are aware or understand the concept of international migration and national security in Nigeria.

DATA ANALYSIS

Table 3: Response rates for causes of international migration in national security

Questions	SD	D	A	SA	Min	Max	Mean	Std.
Porous borders and corruption were factors responsible for international migration in national security	55	28	118	99	1.00	5.00	4.00	0.862
Poverty and population mobility were reasons for international migration in national security	34	22	198	46	1.00	5.00	2.97	0.671
Lapses and abuse of ECOWAS protocol is one of the reasons for international migration in national security	30	16	54	200	1.00	5.00	4.02	0.599

Source: Field Survey Data, 2024

In table 4, on whether porous borders and corruption were factors responsible for international migration in national security, 55 respondents strongly disagreed, 28 respondents disagreed, 118 respondents agreed and 99 respondents strongly agreed as it is evident that 72% (217 out of 300) respondents disagreed. This implies that porous borders and corruption were factors responsible for international migration in national security.

On whether poverty and population mobility were reasons for international migration in national security, 34 respondents strongly disagreed, 22 respondents agreed, 198 agreed and 46 strongly agreed. This indicates that poverty and population mobility were reasons for international migration in national security.

On whether “lapses and abuse of ECOWAS protocol is one of the reasons for international migration in national security” 30 respondents strongly disagreed, 16 respondents disagreed, 54 agreed and 200 strongly agreed. This is to show that lapses and abuse of ECOWAS protocol is one of the reasons for international migration in national security.

Table 4: Response rates for effect of international migration on national security

Questions	SD	D	A	SA	Min	Max	Mean	Std.
International migration leads to infiltration of terrorist and rise in criminal gangs in national security	65	18	99	118	1.00	5.00	4.00	0.673
Political instability and unhealthy political environment were effects of international migration on national security	22	34	219	25	1.00	5.00	2.97	0.956
Health-related diseases, smuggling of illicit business and trafficking in international migration negatively affect national security	40	6	24	230	1.00	5.00	4.02	0.789

Source: Field Survey Data, 2022

In table 4, on whether international migration leads to infiltration of terrorist and rise in criminal gangs in national security, 65 respondents strongly disagreed, 18 respondents disagreed, 99 respondents agreed and 118 respondents strongly agreed. This implies that international migration leads to infiltration of terrorist and rise in criminal gangs in national security.

Whether political instability and unhealthy political environment were effects of international migration on national security, 22 respondents strongly disagreed, 34 respondents agreed, 219 agreed and 25 strongly agreed. This indicates that political instability and unhealthy political environment were effects of international migration on national security.

Whether health-related diseases, smuggling of illicit business and trafficking in international migration negatively affect national security” 40 respondents strongly disagreed, 6 respondents disagreed, 24 agreed and 230 strongly agreed. This is to show that health-related diseases, smuggling of illicit business and trafficking in international migration negatively affect national security.

Table 5: Response rates for strategies to manage international migration in national security

Questions	SD	D	A	SA	Min	Max	Mean	Std.
Community engagement would help to monitor international migration in national security	55	28	118	99	1.00	5.00	4.00	0.708
The government should strengthen co-operation among security agencies in international migration to enhance national security	17	35	200	48	1.00	5.00	3.92	0.966
Proper documentation and biometric and digital measures to track migrants should be adopted in international migration to mitigate issues that border on national security	27	40	120	113	1.00	5.00	3.67	0.874

Source: Field Survey Data, 2024

In table 5, whether community engagement would help to monitor international migration in national security. 55 respondents strongly disagreed, 28 respondents disagreed, 118 respondents agreed and 99 respondents strongly agreed. This implies that community engagement would help to monitor international migration in national security.

Whether the government should strengthen co-operation among security agencies in international migration to enhance national security, 17 respondents strongly disagreed, 35 respondents disagreed, 200 respondents agreed and 48 strongly agreed. This implies that co-operation among security agencies in international migration to enhance national security.

Whether proper documentation and biometric and digital measures to track migrants in international migration would mitigate issues that border on national security. 27 respondents strongly disagreed, 40 disagreed, 120 agreed and 113 strongly agreed. This indicates that proper documentation and biometric and digital measures to track migrants in international migration would mitigate issues that border on national security.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Causes of migration in national security: The causes of international migration differ from individual to individual and from community to community (Mohammed, 2021). The scholar noted that sociologists have long analysed migration issues with the “push-pull” model. “Push factor” refers to circumstances at home that propel to migrate. He listed examples “push factor” to include famine, drought, low agricultural productivity, and unemployment while “pull factor” refers to those conditions found elsewhere (abroad) that attract migrants. Reacting to the above, an interviewee revealed that:

The economic models do look at relative wealth and income between home and destination countries; they do not necessarily imply that international immigrants are always impoverished by standards of the home country. The poorest classes in developing countries may lack the resources needed to cross illegally, or the connections to friends or family already in the destination country (T. Alamina, personal communication, July 25, 2024).

The above simply revealed that poverty is a disease which has presented Nigeria in the picture or receiving end of the effects of illegal international migrants despite that Nigeria is the 6th largest producer of petroleum in the world and the 8th largest exporter with the 10th largest proven reserves (Aliome, 2019).

Following the above cause of international migration in national security, the National Emergency Management Agency in Nigeria (NEMA) has reported that about 12 million people in the region are at risk of hunger. This continued influx of foreigners engenders conflicts over the scarce food resources in Nigeria. The food crisis in Niger has also impacted negatively on the pastoralists and the herdsmen who move down south in search of pasture for their animals. In pastoral areas, production is 66% below national needs. The organization noted that due to pressures from desertification and drought, some foreign pastoralists have shifted their migratory routes southwards into Nigeria in search of animal fodder and better grazing. This has resulted in the herdsmen migrating to the southern part of Niger and other neighbouring countries, including Nigeria to find pasture, a situation that is causing clashes between them and farmers on their trail which undermines national security.

Okeoghene (2017) claimed that youth unemployment and its corollary, underemployment, has become a central political-security issue in Nigeria, in addition to being a socio-economic one. He stressed that the problem which has led to the migration of people to different countries seeking a means of livelihood comes with dire consequences of conflicts and instability within the region. Corroborating the above, an interviewee responded that:

These young men and women in search of work move from one country to the other and, in most cases, end up being recruited into criminal and terrorist groups. In some countries, such as Sierra Leone, the number of young people lacking proper work exceeds 50%. Northern Nigeria which boasts of a large number of able bodied and unskilled youths have come under the influence of terrorist and criminal groups, ready to take up arms in exchange for money (R. Iwedi, personal communication, July 22, 2024).

Udenta & Nwosuji (2015) noted that the Boko Haram terrorist group in Northern Nigeria consists mostly of young men recruited as a result of their lack of means of livelihood. They revealed that it has been established that there is a link between the Boko Haram sect and external radical forces in the region, especially the Al-Qaeda in Maghreb, while Mali and other countries like Sudan are mentioned as training grounds for the sect. Cross-border recruitment of young people as mercenaries in armed conflict is all too common in the arc of territory extending from Guinea-Bissau to Côte d'Ivoire, combined with many other cross-border problems in West Africa, including small arms, mercenaries, illegal check-points and drug-trafficking. This, as a matter of fact, is causing insecurities in the domestic internal affairs of each nation as well as in the region. Discussing the causes of international migration in national security, Akinterinwa (2018) averred that Nigeria's oil resource endowments and huge oil sector earnings has led to the influx of persons from neighbouring countries in search for economic fortune. In addition, the professional and skilled immigrants were recruited as mostly teachers in secondary schools in the country. Following the collapse of the oil prices in the international market in the early 1980s and its devastating impact on the Nigerian economy, the situation took a different turn.

The study wrapped it up by identifying porous borders, abuse of ECOWAS protocol, globalization/manpower problem, inadequate cooperation between security agencies, educational opportunities, lack of social safety, poor governance, corruption, lack of social justice, equity, and fair play, youth unemployment, among others affect national security.

Effect of migration on national security: Igbuzor (2011) opined that the role of border remains a very critical factor in finding solutions to Nigeria national security challenges. He noted that the border protects the country from dangerous and unforeseeable elements. He stressed that Nigeria's borders have become very porous due to years of neglect by Nigeria government. He further revealed that such neglect has led to the serious national security challenges today like Boko Haram insurgency, armed bandit, Herdsmen, illegal bunkering, drug pushing, and weapon trafficking to name but a few which degenerated into the worrisome large scale destruction of lives, properties and economy of the country.

Regrettably, Okeoghene (2017) asserted that the Nigeria national security challenges have become very problematic and cumbersome because of unhindered influx of criminals and arms through the country's porous borders. An interviewee corroborated the fact and responded that:

If a country cannot regulate and control its borderline, there is every tendency that outsiders will infiltrate and unleash mayhem on the citizens of the country and that is exactly what Nigeria is undergoing currently in the hands of Boko Haram insurgency and Fulani Herdsmen. Nigeria undoubtedly has witnessed numerous gruesome attacks on police stations, army barracks, schools, churches, mosques, markets, social gatherings and farms from the hands of the deadly monsters called Boko Haram and Fulani Herdsmen and their attack has continued with impunity while Nigeria government seems helpless (M. Elera, personal communication, July 24, 2024).

Still on the above response, Adeola & Oluyemi (2012) in United Nations Office on Drugs and Crimes (UNODC) noted that the mindless attacks which were illustrated above have led to the death of many security agents and kidnap of countless innocent young girls and boys for sex slavery and forceful conscription, firearm and drug trafficking. They revealed that these are made possible by the Nigeria's

porous border. They further stated that it is estimated that during the dry season, there are more than 10,000 unmanned routes through which trans-border criminals' troop in and out of Nigeria at will.

Fayomi (2013) reported that guns were openly displayed for sale in border areas along Niger and Chad Republics "just like basket of tomatoes". The scholar revealed that in a workshop, Rtd Colonel Hameed Ali who presented the report said "guns are still finding their way into the country in large quantities and that AK-47 gun with 20 rounds of ammunitions goes for N10,000 on Nigeria's borders". With this, it is difficult to have a secured environment.

According to West (2011)

Trans-border crimes could be attributed to several factors including abject poverty, unemployment and lack of governmental presence at the border areas which create a veritable ground for unscrupulous elements to unleash havoc on their target audience. Meanwhile, the complaints of border communities centre on lack of basic socio-economic infrastructure like access roads, schools, clinics, water facilities etc which have not been provided by the government at all levels (p.46).

As noted by Fayomi (2013), the porous nature of Nigeria's borders was responsible for the infiltration of the extremists. Stressing further, the author noted that there are over 1,400 illegal routes, which are not manned. He averred that this has grave security implications for the country and its national immigrations with approximately 23,000 staff strength which was grossly inadequate for the task of policing Nigeria's vast borders. Ani (2010) opined that Nigeria is located in a largely unstable region with volatile socio-political situations in countries like Ivory Coast, Chad, Mali and Cameroon. Easy infiltration of terrorists from Libya and other North African countries and poverty ravaging large sections of the countries' populations make Nigeria susceptible to terrorist pressures. He claimed that in North-Eastern part of the country's border which has the highest concentration of border communities can be listed as the most backward due to most difficult terrain, lowest literacy, and highest poverty rate. He concluded that the combinations of these factors explain why Nigeria record highest number of border related crimes.

Strategies for managing migration in national security: Muhammad (2021) asserted that many questions loom in this discourse. He queried that first; how do we manage migration in the face of national and regional insecurity without impeding ECOWAS efforts at integration? Second, cognizant of the protocol on free movement of persons and goods in ECOWAS integration process, what do we manage – persons, goods or services? This underpins the fact that, in some cases, goods that crisscross our borders have a measure of being lethal and capable of posing insecurities. Therefore, the question now remains, what do we do to address this problem?

A more traditional approach to managing security in many of our borders would be to set up security checks and/or enhance security at the borders of member states, by bringing in more border patrols, police and even soldiers. In that stead, many people and goods will be subjected to stringent and uncompromising scrutiny. On the contrary, individual nations may also decide to close its borders against other citizens and immigrants of Member States, because of the fears that they may be a harbinger of threat and insecurity (Ani, 2010). Adopting this conventional method, which have always been the case with many nations, have also often caused diplomatic brawl amongst them. And for regions where there is offing and a shift towards integration, there are probability that integration as a process for instance in ECOWAS will be truncated, and aside that, it will also constitute a breach of the ECOWAS protocol on free movement of goods and services (Igbuzor, 2011).

Philemon, Manasseh & Godiya (2019) revealed that good governance, economic growth and development should be the priority of governments of member states. He stressed that:

Good governance, as described here, is a system of administration that is democratic, efficient and geared towards the enhancement of economic growth and development. As records have shown, Africa is known to be one of the most fragile continents in the globe. The twenty-first century has seen many African states (especially in West Africa) in conflicts and chaos. Some states within the region are failing, while others have failed and some others are categorized as fragile or weak states. This categorization is predicated on the fact that leadership and governance problems are the foremost push factors that have necessitated economic downturn, conflicts and subsequent migration. Many governments in West Africa are no longer positioned for social provisioning (p.48)

The scholars above claimed that the economic despair in many of the Member States actually triggers their citizens to migrate in search of greener pasture, and, on the other hand, causing insecurity in many of the host countries. An interviewee responded that:

Therein lays the question, if the immigrant mother land is good, why will he or she prefer to go to other countries in search of employment? Therefore, managing migration in the era of national and regional insecurity will mean that many states within the region will have to prioritize their national and economic planning to give room for economic growth, employment and development, as well as being cognizant of issues of climate change and environmental degradation. Recent data have also shown that, in recent times, the after-effect of climate change is also causing huge migration as well as conflict of citizens versus non-indigene which caused so much havoc in some nations of the region, e.g. Côte d'Ivoire (B. Abdullahi, personal communication, June, 15, 2024).

Muhammad (2021) noted that in addition to the effective border patrols and beefing up security, the surest way to manage migration without breaching the Free Movement Protocol, is to ensure an enduring good governance, sustainable economic growth and development, as well as controlled migration within the framework of Articles 3 and 27 of the ECOWAS Treaty both of which provide for free flow of persons, goods and services, by calling on the Member States to ensure graduation removal of all obstacles to free movement of persons, services and capital.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Migration can be a major threat even if it is considered at the individual level, not to mention when it is considered in its group or collective sense. Countries from which migrants are leaving suffer from loss of brain drain and manpower needs, especially when the migrants are highly skilled. In the receiving states, the settlement of migrants also creates the fear of job loss to them. In fact, the truth is that migration has created special fears in the receiving states that an uncontrolled inflow of migrants has the potential to destabilise the cultural settings of the homeland, as well as threaten national security. Nigeria's porous border is the underlying factor that precipitates infiltrations of terrorists, bandits and contraband goods across the country. Nigeria has international land borders of about 4,470 kilometres-2,513 miles and a coastline of 774 kilometres-480 miles which are largely unmanned by security officials. Migration processes are an important factor of socioeconomic, cultural and demographic development and largely determines the state of national security at all levels. This is why uncontrolled migration represents security threat to Nigeria. National security goes beyond military might, defence and law enforcement to include far reaching issues that covers economic, social and political. In sum, migration and national

security remains an integral part of economic activities, movement of goods and services, regional cooperation and territorial integrity and every approach to its proper management should not be swept under the carpet.

The following recommendations are provided by this study.

1. Government should adopt policies that will transform border areas from deplorable conditions and put in place effective and efficient machinery that would speed up developmental process since the underlying causes of international border crimes have links to economic disparity, overpopulation, globalization, manpower problems, corruption, absence of social amenities, poverty, etc.
2. There should be inter-border cooperation with neighbouring government to checkmate the movement of criminals and contraband goods. In other words, government should facilitate collaboration between border personnel for effective border policing.
3. The government should embark on a good governance crusade and invest aggressively in modern military technology which will not only enhance the standard of the security of the border but will curtail the incursion of criminal elements into the country.

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